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The Use of ChatGPT in the Intelligence Era: A Quantitative Study among College Students

Cristyl Angle L. Sombrio,* Linagyn G. Cubio
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the level of the use of ChatGPT among college students across all programs in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. The study utilized quantitative research design in a descriptive-comparative approach in the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. A sample of 257 randomly selected students answered the survey. Also, this study utilized stratified random sampling where the researcher divided the population into subgroups (strata) based on some relevant characteristics, such as age, gender, or academic performance, and then selecting a random sample from each stratum or subgroup. The study utilized adopted questionnaires for the ChatGPT that is appropriate for the context of the study. In addition, the data was analyzed through the use of mean to evaluate the gathered data and null hypothesis to assess the probability of observing of the data under specific assumption. Further, the Likert Scale was used as basis in describing the level of the use of ChatGPT and the respondents would respond by checking a point or circling a number. Results showed that the highest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was for the age of 19 respondents. While the highest frequency goes to the female respondents in terms of sex. Results also revealed that there is a significant difference on the levels on the use of ChatGPT in terms of age, sex and programs among college students.

Keywords: *use of ChatGPT, college students, descriptive-quantitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

ChatGPT is a chatbot driven by generative AI technology that allows you to have a human-like conversations and much more. A lot of challenges about the wide use of ChatGPT occurs and has been associated with several issues that includes privacy concerns, security threats, and biases. Complications exist about the negative impacts or effects of AI tools like ChatGPT specially on college students including plagiarism and cheating in which they use it to complete their assignments which can undermine learning and their academic integrity. Over reliance on the use of ChatGPT for writing assistance might diminish students' ability or skills to write and to think critically. It could merely decline independence and creativity (Atlas, 2023).

In the global setting, specifically in University of Calgary, Canada, recent challenges have been reported to their educational system especially the use of ChatGPT. Teachers and professors are inviting ChatGPT into the classroom, amid debate about ethics, plagiarism and other potential pitfalls. Teachers considers its impact on education in which it should be banned because some of the students rely on it and cannot focus on their own critical thinking skills and diminish their creativity. Another professor reveals that the wide use of this AI tool reduces the learner's motivation and encouragement because students know that they can't do specific tasks without the help of ChatGPT (Wong, 2022).

In the national setting, particularly in University of the Visayas, Cebu City, some cases reported revealed that a lot of issues and concerns about the use of ChatGPT of college students upon its integration to their educational system. The education community has had conflicting feelings on this AI tool as the students utilize recent technology to cheat on essays, exams, and even examinations. In this case, some educators have become alarmed because most of the students are approaching it more liberally and think it has the potential to revolutionize education which is wrong. Using ChatGPT limit the knowledge of the students for the reason that they notice that some of the students who use this AI tool lack their social communication and their own development (Ayman, 2020).

Given the significance of this issue, it is essential to conduct a study. This study is necessary due to numerous concerns regarding biases in AI-generated content, privacy issues, copyright implications, inaccuracies, and plagiarism. As AI systems like ChatGPT become increasingly integrated into everyday life, it is important to understand its societal impact. As such, having this study is quite relevant for the improvement of the school community as this could give valuable information on how to utilize the advancements of artificial tools that would give a new perspective to the students here in our locality. Given that technology use is a primary concern on campus, the study encourages students to better understand concepts through practical application. Thus, it aims to yield positive outcomes, particularly for college students, and assist teachers in prioritizing active learning during class time.

Several studies related to the use of ChatGPT was the study of Firat (2020) entitled "Study and Analysis of ChatGPT and its Impact on Different Fields of Study" specifically in India, which revealed that the use of ChatGPT could limit the creativity and thinking skills of the students by offering them an instant solution and preventing them from brainstorming. There is a lack of research on the long-term effects of chatbot-assisted English learning on speaking competence such as students' interest, belief, motivation and anxiety. Also, the study of Altman (2022) entitled "ChatGPT and Academic Research: A Review and Recommendations Based on the Practical Examples" particularly in Malaysia, clearly states that issues of the wide use of ChatGPT is merely inevitable and cannot be avoided in this area that is why they set a guideline where it would be suitable for usage. According to the study, guidelines should highly imposed because the use of AI tool is unethical in their educational system. Another study of Adarkwah (2023) entitled "What if the

Devil is my Guardian Angel: ChatGPT as a Case Study of Using Chatbots in Education” particularly in China, revealed various issues including cheating and misuse. A lot of concerns coming from an advanced chatbot, such as ChatGPT were not well investigated in the education field. Therefore, it is not clear if ChatGPT will overcome the concerns found in the previous chatbots or will even deepen them. Additionally, there is a need for more research on the specific pedagogical implications and methods for effectively using chatbots in the educational environment.

After completing this research, strategic efforts will be undertaken to disseminate the findings to both readers and the academic community, fostering further discussion and practical application. The versatility of ChatGPT, with its wide range of applications—from content generation to language translation—makes it highly accessible and user-friendly for various audiences, including both professionals and casual users. These attributes of ChatGPT highlight its potential as a powerful tool for enhancing productivity and improving learning experiences across multiple fields. To maximize the study's impact, complimentary copies will be provided to participating schools, and the research will be presented at various conferences. Efforts will also be made to publish the research in a peer-reviewed journal to reach a wider audience and contribute to academic discussions

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to determine the level of the use of ChatGPT among college students in terms of age, sex, and program. Specifically, it sought to answer to the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. program
2. To determine the level of the use of ChatGPT of college students in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic motivation;
 - 2.2. perceived ease of use; and
 - 2.3. behavioral intention
3. To gauge the significant difference of ChatGPT use in terms of:
 - 3.1. age;
 - 3.2. sex; and
 - 3.3. program

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design utilizing the descriptive approach, quantitative method employs strategies of study such as surveys and collect data on determined instruments that yield statistic data. Thus, quantitative research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. It can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships and generalize results to wider population (Bhandari, 2020).

In the context of this study, the researcher utilized quantitative research on the use of ChatGPT to collect and analyze numerical data to understand patterns, behaviors, getting the frequency and the overall effectiveness of the technology. Furthermore, the researcher was conducting quantitative surveys which allow to gather numerical ratings of user satisfaction, usability, and overall experience. Quantitative research plays a critical role in understanding and improving ChatGPT by providing structured, numerical data that can be analyzed to draw meaningful conclusions.

Descriptive research is particularly suitable when the objective is to examine and identify specific characteristics, frequencies, patterns, and categories. While it is predominantly classified as a form of quantitative research, qualitative approaches can also be employed for descriptive analysis. It is essential to carefully craft the research design to ensure that the outcomes are both credible and dependable (McCombes, 2023).

In the context of this study, the researcher utilized descriptive research which aims to document students' opinions, attitudes, and levels of trust on the use of ChatGPT. It may involve surveys or interviews to gauge students' satisfaction, perceptions of reliability, concerns about bias or accuracy, and general acceptance of AI-driven tools. Gathering this information helps to understand how comfortable students are with using ChatGPT and whether they view it as a trustworthy, usefulness and ethical tool.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the college students from all programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST) during the second semester of A.Y. 2023-2024. They were chosen as the respondents because they suited for the study and since it involved the use of ChatGPT, it is fitting and valid to include students from all programs in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST). Further, to establish randomness and maintain the element of science in the study, stratified random sampling is chosen.

The research employed stratified random sampling as its sampling technique. This method involved segmenting the population into distinct subgroups or strata based on key characteristics such as age, gender, or academic performance, and then randomly selecting participants from each subgroup. Stratified random sampling ensures that the sample is representative of the population, with each subgroup being properly represented, thereby enhancing the generalizability of the results. However, this technique necessitates a well-defined population and a clear understanding of the relevant characteristics for effective stratification (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

The stratified random sampling is particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents of this research had been randomly selected based on the strata, which were in this case, the students from all programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST). To compute the sample, the researcher first gathered the data on the population of respondents by writing a formal request letter to the college registrar, requesting access to the population of respondents. After getting the data, the researcher sent this information to her statistician for the computation of the study sample. Consequently, the statistician provides the following computed data, indicating the sample appropriate for the study.

Table 1 shows the research data where the study's respondents were presented, in which there were 257 samples drawn from a population of 6,954 college students across all programs. The respondents that qualified in the study were the young adults aged 18 to 29 years old, male and female, and definitely students who are currently studying at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology (KCAST).

In addition, the programs that included in the study were the Bachelor of Agricultural Technology (BAT), Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), Bachelor of Public Administration (BPA), Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (BSA), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), Bachelor of Science in Criminology (BSC), Bachelor of Science in Office Administration (BSOA), Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED). Further, the respondents who did not qualified in this study were the members of the LGBTQ+, teens aged 13-17 years old, adults aged 40-60 years old, and the teachers in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Program	Sex	Population	Sample	Percentage(%)
BAT	Male	102	4	0.05
	Female	81	3	0.04
BEED	Male	43	2	0.02
	Female	270	10	0.14
BPA	Male	455	17	0.24
	Female	478	18	0.25
BSA	Male	298	11	0.16
	Female	184	7	0.10
BSBA	Male	758	28	0.40
	Female	1130	42	0.60
BSA	Male	769	28	0.41
	Female	519	19	0.28
BSOA	Male	304	11	0.16
	Female	634	23	0.34
BSED	Male	265	10	0.14
	Female	666	25	0.35
TOTAL		6954	257	3.70%

Instrument

The researcher utilized an adopted questionnaires for the dependent variable that is appropriate for the context of this study. The first set of questions dealt on the level of the use of ChatGPT with its (3) indicators: intrinsic motivation, perceived ease of use, and behavioral intention from the study of Kung (2022).

The Likert Scale was used as basis in describing the level of the use of ChatGPT. In this scale, Zulueta and Perez (2010) explained that the respondents would respond by checking a point or circling a number. The checks were assigned with numerical values. These values were totaled over the items to give the respondents an altitude score.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researcher performed the following steps.

Crafting Questionnaire. The researcher adapted questionnaires for a single variable. To make the questionnaire suitable for the respondents, the researcher modifies and conceptualize it this helps the researcher to achieve her research objectives. After the modification of the questionnaires, it was submitted to the panel of experts for validation.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher asked permission from the VPAA- Office of the Vice President of Academic Affairs of KCAST, through a letter to allow the researcher to conduct study among English major students. Upon the approval of the Vice President of Academic Affairs to administer the questionnaire, the researcher provided the respondents the information about the study and allowed them to make an informed decision whether to participate or not.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. Lastly, after conducting the research, the researcher verified and gathered the research instrument in preparation for tabulating. The tabulation was done by my statistician, Ms. Regine L. Generalao, MST-Math. The findings were interpreted to draw conclusions and recommendations were made on the study's findings.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure the proper conduct of this research as well as the safety of those involved, the researcher strictly adhered to the highest ethical standards suggested by Denzin and Lincoln (2011) as well as Lune and Berg (2017). This includes the following components: Informed Consent, Risk of Harm, Anonymity and Confidentiality; and Conflict of Interest.

Firstly, informed consent is the process of giving permission for something to occur or for an action to be taken, based on a complete understanding of all relevant information, including potential risks and available alternatives. It is an essential safeguard in research in which it has an obligation to obtain respect for persons and a desire to respect the autonomy of the individual deciding whether to participate in the process (Siegle, 2019).

In the context of this study, the researcher allowed the respondents to voluntarily participate in the study and let them make an informed decision about whether or not to sign up for the research study or continue participating. The researcher also ensured that participants fully understood the study by asking them to repeat back the project's purpose and what their participation entailed, serving as a confirmation of their comprehension of the consent process. This method guaranteed that participants made well-informed and voluntary decisions regarding their involvement. It underscored the necessity for transparent, open, and honest communication between the researcher and the participants, fostering a trustworthy and ethical research environment.

Secondly, risk of harm, anonymity and confidentiality means a significant danger that the participants will suffer or abuse. In conducting the study, the researchers have an obligation to minimize risks of harm to participants and manage any residual risks. Also, anonymity and confidentiality refer to an agreement between you and the potential participants that their individual responses and identities will not be disclosed beyond the research team unless they have agreed otherwise (Zach, 2020).

In the context of this study, the researcher remained vigilant to the potential range of harms that could arise from research activities and implemented appropriate measures to prevent foreseeable risks. It was the researcher's responsibility to cultivate a safe and inclusive environment to protect respondents from harm. Additionally, participants were given the choice to decide whether to disclose their names. This emphasized the researcher's duty to follow specific procedures and methods during the data collection and dissemination process to ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of participants whenever applicable. Furthermore, it was crucial for the researcher to recognize and respect participants' rights to protect their identities from being revealed and to maintain the confidentiality of their records.

Finally, a conflict of interest occurs when an individual's personal interests or stakes in the outcome of a research study have the potential to influence the results, either in reality or in appearance, thereby compromising the integrity and objectivity of the research. It was also a situation where professional objectivity maybe compromised, or perceived to be compromised because of competing financial, personal or other personal considerations may compromise and judgements in conducting research (Kluwer, 2018).

In the context of this study, the researcher had to carefully assess the potential for conflicts of interest across all involved parties and recognized that perceived conflicts could be just as significant as actual ones. This underscored the importance of ensuring that researchers engaged in human research avoided any real or perceived conflicts of interest, particularly those related to financial interests, in connection with the studies they were conducting. By maintaining transparency and integrity in their relationships and obligations, researchers upheld the ethical standards necessary to foster trust and credibility in their work.

Results and Discussion

In the section, discussions were presented concerning the data on the use of ChatGPT of college students across all programs in the research locale. This included the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and program, level of the use of ChatGPT of college students in terms of intrinsic motivation, the level of the use of ChatGPT of college students in terms of perceived ease of use and the level of the use of ChatGPT of college students in terms of behavioral intention of students as well as the significant difference of ChatGPT in terms of age, sex and program.

The Profile of Respondents in Terms of Age

Table 2 presented the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The data revealed that the highest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained from age of 19 which has a total of 20.62%. This means that most of the students who are using ChatGPT were aged 19 years old.

Also, the data revealed that the second highest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained from the age of 20 which has the total of 19.07%. This means that students aged 20 are frequently utilizing ChatGPT. Moreover, the third highest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained from the age of 22 which has a total of 15.18%. Followed by aged 23 which has a total of 14.79%, aged 21 which has a total of 12.06%, aged 18 which has a total of 8.56% and aged 24 which has a total of 6.23%

Lastly, the data revealed that the lowest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained from the age of 25 respondents which has a total of 1.17%. This means that most of the students of KCAST aged 19 were rarely utilizing ChatGPT. Also, the data revealed that the second lowest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained from the age of 26 which has a total of 2.33%. This means that students aged 26 in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology were rarely utilizing ChatGPT.

Table 2. *Profile of Respondents in Terms of Age*

Age	Frequency	Percent
18	22	8.56%
19	53	20.62%
20	49	19.07%
21	31	12.06%
22	39	15.18%
23	38	14.79%
24	16	6.23%
25	3	1.17%
26	6	2.33%
Total	257	100%

The Profile of Respondents in Terms of Sex

Table 3 presented the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. The data revealed that the highest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained from the female respondents which has a total of 20.62%. This means that most of the students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology are female students who are frequently utilizing ChatGPT.

Further, the data revealed that male respondents have the lowest frequency on the use of ChatGPT which has a total of 4.92%. This means that most of the students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology were male students who are rarely utilizing ChatGPT.

Table 3. *Profile of Respondents in Terms of Sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	146	56.81%
Male	111	43.19%
Total	257	100%

The Profile of Respondents in Terms of Program

Table 4 presented the profile of the respondents in terms of program. The data revealed that the highest frequency on the use of ChatGPT was obtained by the BSBA respondents which has a total of 29.57%. This means that most of the students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology are BSBA students who are frequently utilizing ChatGPT.

Table 4. *Profile of Respondents in Terms of Program*

Program	Frequency	Percent
BAT	7	2.72%
BEED	12	4.67%
BPA	35	13.62%
BSA	18	7.00%
BSBA	76	29.57%
BSC	47	18.29%
BSED	28	10.89%
BSOA	34	13.23%
Total	257	100%

Furthermore, the second-highest frequency of ChatGPT usage was recorded among students from the BSC program, accounting for 18.29%. This clearly indicates that students in the BSC program at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology are the second most frequent users of ChatGPT. In addition, the third-highest usage was observed among students from the BPA program, with a rate of 13.62%.

This suggests that students in the BPA program are the third most frequent users. Following this, the fourth-highest frequency was recorded among students in the BSOA program, showing a usage rate of 13.23%. This implies that BSOA students are the fourth most frequent users of ChatGPT.

Moreover, the BSED program students registered the fifth-highest usage, with a rate of 10.89%. This highlights that students in the BSED program are the fifth most frequent users. Finally, the sixth-highest frequency was noted among students from the BSA program, with a usage rate of 7.00%. This demonstrates that students in the BSA program are the sixth most frequent users of ChatGPT.

Lastly, the data revealed that students from the BAT program had the second-lowest frequency of ChatGPT usage, at 2.72%. This means that BAT students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology are among the least likely to use ChatGPT. On the other hand, BEED students recorded the lowest usage frequency, with a rate of just 4.67%. This indicates that students in the BEED program at the same college are the least frequent users of ChatGPT, suggesting that they rarely engage with the tool.

Level on the Use of ChatGPT in Terms Intrinsic Motivation

The level of the use of ChatGPT of college students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, intrinsic motivation. The responses on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 5 presented the levels on the use of ChatGPT among college students concerning intrinsic motivation. The data revealed that the levels on the use of ChatGPT, as perceived by college students in terms of intrinsic motivation, had an overall mean score of 3.82, which corresponds to a high level. This suggests that the level on the use of ChatGPT, particularly in terms of intrinsic motivation, was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items in terms of intrinsic motivation is 3.91, which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This mean is from Item No.5 - Seeking new opportunities to overcome difficulties in making outputs. This means that the item was oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Further, the lowest mean score among the survey items in terms of intrinsic motivation is 3.75, which indicates a high level. This means that the Item No.1 - Finding ChatGPT enjoyable was oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 5. *Level on Use of ChatGPT of College Students in Terms of Intrinsic Motivation*

Intrinsic Motivation	Mean	Description
1. Finding ChatGPT enjoyable	3.75	High
2. Allowing myself to express my thoughts using ChatGPT	3.77	High
3. Finding myself more skillful and motivated using ChatGPT	3.79	High
4. Setting my goal to gain more information	3.90	High
5. Seeking new opportunities to overcome difficulties in making outputs.	3.91	High
OVERALL	3.82	High

Level of the Use of ChatGPT in Terms of Perceived Ease of Use

The level on the use of ChatGPT for college students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, perceived ease of use. The responses on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 6 displayed the levels on the use of ChatGPT for college students concerning perceived ease of use. The data revealed that the level on the use of ChatGPT in terms of perceived ease of use, had an overall mean score of 3.73, which corresponds to a high level. This suggests that the level on the use of ChatGPT of college students, particularly in terms of perceived ease of use, was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items in terms of perceived ease of use is 3.83, which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the Item No.1 – Learning immediately how to use ChatGPT was oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

Further, the lowest mean score among the survey items in terms of perceived ease of use is 3.54, which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This is from Item No. 4 - Feeling comfortable using ChatGPT without any help or assistance which means that it is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 6. *Level on Use of ChatGPT of College Students in Terms of Perceived Ease of Use*

Perceived Ease of Use	Mean	Description
1. Learning immediately how to use ChatGPT	3.83	High
2. Recommending ChatGPT to others based on its ease of use	3.81	High
3. Finding ChatGPT convenient and effective	3.79	High
4. Feeling comfortable using ChatGPT without any help or assistance	3.54	High
5. Did not encounter difficulties while using ChatGPT	3.65	High
OVERALL	3.73	High

Level of the Use of ChatGPT of College Students in Terms of Behavioral Intention

The level on the use of ChatGPT for college students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, behavioral intention. The responses on the indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 7 presented the levels on the use of ChatGPT for college students with regard to their behavioral intention. The data revealed that the level on the use of ChatGPT as perceived by college students in terms of behavioral intention, had an overall mean score of

3.81, which corresponds to a high level. This suggests that the level on the use of ChatGPT of college students, particularly in terms of behavioral intention was oftentimes observed.

The highest mean score among the survey items in terms of behavioral intention is 3.91 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the Item No.5 - Believing that ChatGPT is helpful in the future is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Further, the lowest mean score among the survey items in terms of behavioral intention is 3.65 which indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the Item No. 2 - Committing myself to use ChatGPT in my tasks or activities is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 7. Level on Use of ChatGPT of College Students in Terms of Behavioral Intention

Behavioral Intention	Mean	Description
1. Wanting to discover new ways to utilize ChatGPT	3.83	High
2. Committing myself to use ChatGPT in my tasks or activities	3.65	High
3. Wisely manage my limitations using ChatGPT	3.85	High
4. Sharing my positive experiences upon using ChatGPT	3.77	High
5. Believing that ChatGPT is helpful in the future	3.91	High
OVERALL	3.81	High

Summary on the Level of the Use of ChatGPT among College Students

Table 8 provides an overview of the overall level on the use of ChatGPT for college students, bearing in mind with intrinsic motivation, perceived ease of use, and behavioral intention.

Table 8. Summary on the Level of the Use of ChatGPT Among College Students

Indicators	Mean	Description
Intrinsic Motivation	3.82	High
Perceived Ease of Use	3.73	High
Behavioral Intention	3.81	High
OVERALL	3.79	High

The data revealed that the overall use of ChatGPT of college students, had a total mean score of 3.79 falling within the high range. This suggests that the level on the use of ChatGPT among college students was oftentimes observed and consistently considered to be of high.

Further, the highest mean score among the indicators is 3.82 which belongs to the indicator, intrinsic motivation. This, therefore, indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the level on the use of ChatGPT among college students in terms of intrinsic motivation is oftentimes observed.

Furthermore, the lowest mean score among the indicators is 3.73 which belongs to the indicator, perceived ease of use. This, therefore, indicates a high level of agreement among the respondents. This means that the level on the use of ChatGPT among college students in terms of perceived ease of use is oftentimes observed.

Lastly, it is worth noting that the behavioral intention, which is the second-highest, obtained a mean score of 3.81, signifying a high level on the use of ChatGPT. this suggests that the usage of ChatGPT among college students in terms of behavioral intention, was oftentimes observed and consistently considered to be high.

Significant Difference of ChatGPT Use in Terms of Age, Sex and Program

Table 9 illustrates a significant difference in the use of ChatGPT across age, gender, and academic program. The findings revealed an F-value of 5.81 and a P-value of less than 0.001, which is below the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there is a meaningful difference in the use of ChatGPT based on age. Additionally, the results revealed a t-value of 0.264 and a p-value of 0.792, both of which are above the 0.05 significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis was not rejected, indicating that there is no significant difference in the use of ChatGPT based on gender.

Table 9. Significant Difference of ChatGPT Use in Terms of Age, Sex and Program

Variable	Mean	F-Value * t-Value #	P-Value	Decision
Age	31.27	5.81*	<.001	H ₀ Rejected
Sex	5.68	0.264 #	0.792	H ₀ Accepted
Program	26.79	2.592 *	0.013	H ₀ Rejected

Lastly, results showed in the study that F-Value (2.592) and P-Value (0.013) at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was being rejected. This means that there is a significant difference on the use of ChatGPT in terms of program.

In summary, the table indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected, signifying a significant difference in the use of ChatGPT among students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology based on age and academic program. Conversely, the null hypothesis was accepted regarding gender, suggesting that there is no significant difference in the use of ChatGPT among students at the college based on sex. It also means that most of the male and female students are frequently utilizing ChatGPT.

Conclusions

This section consists of an overall summary of the study, with a particular focus on the results and their implications. The conclusions drawn in response to the study objectives are as follows:

It was concluded that the level on the use of ChatGPT, is high. This means that the variable is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

The results indicated that the null hypothesis was rejected, signifying a significant difference in the use of ChatGPT based on age. Additionally, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no significant difference in its use based on gender. Finally, the study found that the null hypothesis was rejected regarding academic program, showing a significant difference in ChatGPT usage across different programs. Consequently, the researcher concludes that age and academic program have a statistically significant impact on the use of ChatGPT, while no significant difference was found in relation to sex.

Among the indicators of the levels on the use of ChatGPT, it was determined that perceived ease of use was discovered the lowest mean. Hence, the following recommendations are provided. First, for the perceived ease of use, it is recommended to integrate the use of ChatGPT in making short and simple sentences to improve readability of the learners and to avoid complicated explanations. Second, for the intrinsic motivation, it is recommended to utilize ChatGPT in any language games, puzzles and debates where students can find challenges and satisfaction of solving puzzles or winning games that can increase engagement with the language without the need of external rewards. Lastly, for the behavioral intention, it is recommended to use ChatGPT in multimedia projects in school such as creating English-language podcasts, vlogs, recording and editing projects. Through this, the creative process and potential for sharing their work with others make students more engaged and motivated to use English outside of traditional classroom settings.

Additionally, it is essential to provide training for instructors on the ethical use of ChatGPT to ensure responsible integration into their teaching practices. These training sessions should cover key topics such as data privacy, the limitations of AI-generated content, and strategies for preventing over-reliance on the tool. By equipping instructors with a solid understanding of the ethical considerations surrounding ChatGPT, they can better guide students in using the tool responsibly.

Moreover, training can emphasize how to balance AI usage with traditional teaching methods, ensuring that ChatGPT complements rather than replaces critical thinking and independent research. In combination with exploring innovative ways to integrate ChatGPT into teaching, providing such training will help create a well-rounded, ethically sound approach to using AI in education. This will not only enhance learning outcomes but also cultivate a responsible, thoughtful, and innovative academic environment.

Also, it would be beneficial to organize seminars for both instructors and students on the responsible use of ChatGPT. These seminars could offer practical training on how to ethically integrate ChatGPT into academic work, highlighting real-world examples and best practices. Such initiatives will not only foster ethical awareness but also promote critical thinking about AI's role in education, helping both instructors and students navigate the complexities of AI-generated content responsibly. By combining clear guidelines, ongoing discussions, and educational seminars, institutions can cultivate a culture of ethical AI usage, ensuring that ChatGPT is used as a tool to enhance learning while maintaining academic integrity.

In addition, it is definitely recommended to undertake research studies that systematically analyze the advantages and disadvantages of ChatGPT across various contexts, such as in education, business and personal use. This includes qualitative and quantitative methods, including surveys, interviews, focus group discussions, and case studies. Comprehensive research provides a deeper understanding of how ChatGPT is perceived and utilized, highlighting both benefits and drawbacks in real-world applications. Conduct comparative studies that evaluate ChatGPT and other AI tools will do that could help contextualize its capabilities and limitations.

Moreover, based on the result, which states that the moderating variable, age and program has a significant difference on the levels on the use of ChatGPT. It is hereby recommended that for the school to implement workshops for teachers and students by conducting training sessions to familiarize everyone on how to use ChatGPT properly, effectively and ethically. In addition, it is recommended that more studies to be conducted to identify the others benefits of integrating ChatGPT into research processes to enhance efficiency, foster innovation, facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, and provide valuable support across various stages of the research lifecycle.

References

Abbasi, G.A., Sandran, T., Ganesan, Y., & Iranmanesh, M. (2022). Go cashless! Determinants of continuance intention to use E-wallet apps: A hybrid approach using PLS-SEM and fsQCA. *Technology in Society*, 68, 101937.

Abdelghani, R., Wang, Y. H., Yuan, X., Wang, T., Sauzon, H., & Oudeyer, P. Y. (2022). GPT-3-driven pedagogical agents to train

- children's curious question-asking skills. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 1–36. <https://doi.org/>
- Abdullah, F., & Ward, R. (2016). Developing a general extended technology acceptance model for E-learning (GETAMEL) by analyzing commonly used external factors. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 56, 238–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.11.036>
- Adarkwah, M. A., Amponsah, S., van Wyk, M. M., Huang, R., Tlili, A., Shehata, B., & Metwally, A. H. S. (2023). Awareness and acceptance of ChatGPT as a generative conversational AI for transforming education by Ghanaian academics: A two-phase study. *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching*, 6(2), 78–93. <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.2.26>
- Ahmed, M. (2024). Impact of ChatGPT on Academic Writing at Moroccan Universities. *Arab World English Journal Special Issue on ChatGPT*, 4–25. <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/ChatGPT.1>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Aleedy, M., Atwell, E., & Meshoul, S. (2022). Using AI chatbots in education: Recent advances, challenges, and use cases. In *Artificial Intelligence and Sustainable Computing: Proceedings of ICSISCET 2021*.
- Ali, M. (2023). Exploring the dimensions of ChatGPT in English language learning: A global perspective. *Library Hi Tech. Ahead-of-print*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LHT-05-2023-0200>
- Alkaissi, H., & McFarlane, S. I. (2023). Artificial hallucinations in ChatGPT: Implications in scientific writing. *Cureus*, 15, e35179.
- Alshater, M. (2022). Exploring the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing academic performance: A case study of ChatGPT. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4312358>
- Anders, B. A. (2023). Why ChatGPT is such a big deal for education. *C2C Digital Magazine*, 1(18). https://scholarspace.jccc.edu/c2c_online/vol1/iss18/4
- Amiri, M., Alami, A., Matlabi, M., & Shomoossi, N. (2021). Error analysis of nonnative authors' publications in healthcare journals: A descriptive study. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 10, 107.
- Araujo, G. (2024). Is ChatGPT an effective solver of sentiment analysis tasks in Portuguese? A Preliminary Study. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Processing of Portuguese - Vol. 1* (pp. 13–21). Santiago de Compostela, Galicia/Spain: Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Arif, T. B., Munaf, U., & Ul-Haque, I. (2023). The future of medical education and research: Is ChatGPT a blessing or blight in disguise? *Medical Education Online*, 28, 2181052.
- Aslam, W., Siddiqui, D. A., Arif, I., & Farhat, K. (2022). Chatbots in the frontline: Drivers of acceptance. *Kybernetes*.
- Atlas, S. (2023). ChatGPT for higher education and professional development: A guide to conversational AI. https://digitalcommons.uri.edu/cba_facpubs/548
- Ayman, S. E. (2023). The impact of ChatGPT on student learning/performing. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4532913>
- Azhar, G. S., Azhar, A. Z., & Azhar, A. S. (2012). Overwork among residents in India: A medical resident's perspective. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 1, 141–143.
- Baidoo-Anu, D., & Owusu Ansah, L. (2023). Education in the era of generative artificial intelligence (AI): Understanding the potential benefits of ChatGPT in promoting teaching and learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4337484>
- Baumgartner, C. (2023). The potential impact of ChatGPT in clinical and translational medicine. *Clinical and Translational Medicine*, 13, e1206.
- Belanche, D., Casal, L. V., & Flavian, C. (2019). Artificial intelligence in FinTech: Understanding robo-advisors' adoption among customers. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 119(7), 1411–1430.
- Bernabei, M., Choudhury, M., & Chen, X. (2023). Examining students' intention to use ChatGPT: Insights from the Technology Acceptance Model. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 39(6), 54–73. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.8374>
- Bhattacharyya, M., Miller, V. M., Bhattacharyya, D., & Miller, L. E. (2023). High rates of fabricated and inaccurate references in ChatGPT-generated medical content. *Cureus*, 15, e39238.
- Bhandari, P. (2021). An introduction to correlational research. *Scribbr*.
- Biswas, S. (2023). ChatGPT and the future of medical writing. *Radiology*, 307, e223312. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.223312>
- Bonsu, E. M., & Baffour-Koduah, D. (2023). From the consumers' side: Determining students' perception and intention to use ChatGPT in Ghanaian higher education. *Journal of Education and Social Multiculturalism*, 4(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jesm->

2023-0001

Bonwell, C. C., & Eison, J. A. (1991). Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom. ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Reports. ERIC Clearinghouse on Higher Education, The George Washington University.

Calabrese, C., Ding, J., Millam, B., & Barnett, G. A. (2020). The uproar over gene-edited babies: A semantic network analysis of CRISPR on Twitter. *Environmental Communication*, 14(7), 954–970. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17524032.2019.1699135>

Caratiquit, G. (2024). Examining science education in ChatGPT: An exploratory study of generative artificial intelligence. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*.

Chattaraman, V., Kwon, W. S., Gilbert, J. E., & Ross, K. (2019). Should AI-based conversational digital assistants employ social- or task-oriented interaction style? A task-competency and reciprocity perspective for older adults. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 90, 315–330.

Chocarro, R., Cortiñas, M., & Marcos-Matas, G. (2021). Teachers' attitudes towards chatbots in education: A technology acceptance model approach considering the effect of social language, bot proactiveness, and users' characteristics. *Educational Studies*, 49(2), 1–19. <https://doi.org>

Ciechanowski, L., Przegalinska, A., Magnuski, M., & Gloor, P. (2019). In the shades of the uncanny valley: An experimental study of human–chatbot interaction. *Future Generation Computer Systems*.

Colace, G. (2023). The why, what, and how of publishing a manuscript: A blend of art and science. *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology*, 71, 2930–2931.

Copeland, A. (2024). *Understanding ChatGPT: AI applications and implications in modern society*. OpenAI Press.

Cunningham, A., et al. (2019). Mainstreaming AIED into education? *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 11, 197–207.

Davis, F. D. (1985). A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: Theory and results. Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

Deraga, E., Ciaramella, A., & Consoli, S. (2023). The role of ChatGPT in education: An overview of its potential benefits and challenges. *Educational Sciences*, 14(6), 654. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060654>

Dunn, W. R., Lyman, S., & Marx, R. (2003). Research methodology. *Arthroscopy*, 19, 870–873.

Dwivedi, Y. K., et al. (2023). "So what if ChatGPT wrote it?" Multidisciplinary perspectives on opportunities, challenges, and implications of generative conversational AI for research, practice, and policy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 71, Article 102642. <https://doi.org>

Etikan, I., & Bala, K. (2017). Sampling and sampling methods. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), 149–150.

Farrugia, P., Petrisor, B. A., Farrokhyar, F., & Bhandari, M. (2010). Practical tips for surgical research: Research questions, hypotheses, and objectives. *Canadian Journal of Surgery*, 53, 278–281.

Fernandes, T., & Oliveira, E. (2021). Understanding consumers' acceptance of automated technologies in service encounters: Drivers of digital voice assistants' adoption.

Firat, M., & Bozkurt, A. (2020). Variables affecting online learning readiness in an open and distance learning university. *Educational Media International*, 57(2), 112-127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523987.2020.1786772>.

Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research. Addison-Wesley.

Fishbein, M. (1979). A theory of reasoned action: Some applications and implications. *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation*, 27, 65–116.

Fishman, B. J. (2016). Possible futures for online teacher professional development. In C. Dede, A. Eisenkraft, K. Frumin, & A. Hartley (Eds.), *Teacher learning in the digital age*. Online professional development in STEM education (pp. 3–31). Harvard Education Press.

Fontao, L. (2023). The use of ChatGPT in teaching and learning: A systematic review through SWOT analysis approach. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 160561. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/educ.2023.1160561>.

Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3).

Franke, G., & Sarstedt, M. (2019). Heuristics versus statistics in discriminant validity testing: A comparison of four procedures. *Internet Research*, 29(3), 430-447. <https://doi.org>

- Fütterer, T., Fischer, C., Alekseeva, A., et al. (2023). ChatGPT in education: Global reactions to AI innovations. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 15310. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-42227-6>.
- Gannon, F. (2008). Language barriers. *EMBO Reports*, 9, 207.
- Gelling, L. (2015). Stages in the research process. *Nursing Standard*, 29, 44–49.
- Grájeda, A., Burgos, J., Córdova, P., & Sanjinés, A. (2024). Assessing student-perceived impact of using artificial intelligence tools: Construction of a synthetic index of application in higher education. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), Article 2287917. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2287917>.
- Grewal, A., Kataria, H., & Dhawan, I. (2016). Literature search for research planning and identification of research problem. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*, 60, 635–639.
- Goel, S. (2018). Humility: A key to get published. *Journal of Medical Research and Innovation*, 2, e000087. <https://doi.org/10.15419/jmri.87>.
- Golan, R., Reddy, R., Muthigi, A., & Ramasamy, R. (2023). Artificial intelligence in academic writing: A paradigm-shifting technological advance. *Nature Reviews Urology*, 20, 327–328.
- Gunser, V. E., Gottschling, S., Brucker, B., Richter, S., Çakir, D. C., & Gerjets, P. (2022). The pure poet: How good is the subjective credibility and stylistic quality of literary short texts written with an artificial intelligence tool as compared to texts written by human authors? *Proceedings of the First Workshop on Intelligent and Interactive Writing Assistants (In2Writing 2022)*, 60–61. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.in2writing-1.8>.
- Haenlein, M., Kaplan, A., Tan, C. W., & Zhang, P. (2019). Artificial intelligence (AI) and management analytics. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 6(4), 341-343.
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., & Singh, R. P. (2023). An era of ChatGPT as a significant futuristic support tool: A study on features, abilities, and challenges. *BenchCouncil Transactions on Benchmarks, Standards and Evaluations*, 2, 100089.
- Hamza, S. (2020). The effects of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on continuance intention to use e-government. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35, 644-649.
- Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81–112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487>.
- Haque, M. U., Dharmadasa, I., Sworna, Z. T., Rajapakse, R. N., & Ahmad, H. (2022). Exploring sentiments of ChatGPT early adopters using Twitter data. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2212.05856>.
- Hetler, A. (2023). ChatGPT. *WhatIs.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.techtarget.com/whatis/definition/ChatGPT>
- Honavar, S. G. (2023). Eye of the AI storm: Exploring the impact of AI tools in ophthalmology. *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology*, 71, 2328–2340.
- Hosseini, M., & Horbach, S. P. J. M. (2023). Fighting reviewer fatigue or amplifying bias? Considerations and recommendations for use of ChatGPT and other large language models in scholarly peer review. *Research Integrity and Peer Review*, 8(1), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-023-00133-5>
- Hui, et al. (2021). Active learning as a beyond-the-classroom strategy to improve university students' career adaptability. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6246.
- In, J., & Lee, S. (2017). Statistical data presentation. *Korean Journal of Anesthesiology*, 70, 267–276.
- Ince, J., Rojas, F., & Davis, C. A. (2017). The social media response to Black Lives Matter: How Twitter users interact with Black Lives Matter through hashtag use. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 40(11), 1814–1830. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2017.1334931>
- Wang, J., et al. (2023). On the robustness of ChatGPT: An adversarial and out-of-distribution perspective. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.12095>
- Jahanshahi, H., Kazmi, S., & Cevik, M. (2022). Auto response generation in online medical chat services. *Journal of Healthcare Informatics Research*, 6(3), 344–374.
- Jo, H., & Park, D. H. (2024). Effects of ChatGPT's AI capabilities and human-like traits on spreading information in work environments. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 7806.
- Kalla, D., & Smith, N. (2023). Study and analysis of ChatGPT and its impact on different fields of study. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 8(3), 830–835. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7767675>

- Kalendra, M. (2022). ChatGPT and large language models in academia: Opportunities and challenges. *BioData Mining*, 15, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13040-022-00290-y>
- Kallestinova, E. D. (2011). How to write your first research paper. *Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine*, 84, 181.
- Karam, A. (2017). Informed consent process: A step further towards making it meaningful! *Perspectives in Clinical Research*, 8, 107–112.
- Keiper, M. C., Fried, G., Lupinek, J., & Nordstrom, H. (2023). Artificial intelligence in sport management education: Playing the AI game with ChatGPT. *Journal of Sport and Tourism Education*, 33, 100456.
- Khaneghahi, M., Bagheri, A., & Ranjbar, S. (2022). Adapting to the future: ChatGPT as a means for supporting constructivist learning environments. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education*, 4(1), 21–33.
- Kim, J., Merrill, K., Xu, K., & Kelly, S. (2022). Perceived credibility of an AI instructor in online education: The role of social presence and voice features. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 136, 107383.
- King, M. R., & ChatGPT. (2023). A conversation on artificial intelligence, chatbots, and plagiarism in higher education. *Cellular and Molecular Bioengineering*, 16(1), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1001/cellmolbioeng.2023.0001>
- Kluwer, P. (2018). Conflict of interest and medical journals. *JAMA*, 319(17), 1797–1798. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2018.2856>
- Kohnke, L., Moorhouse, B. L., & Zou, D. (2023). ChatGPT for language teaching and learning. *RELC*, 003368822311628.
- Kung, et al. (2022). Performance of ChatGPT on USMLE: Potential for AI-assisted medical education using large language models. *medRxiv*.
- La Barbera, F., & Ajzen, I. (2020). Control interactions in the theory of planned behavior: Rethinking the role of subjective norm. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*.
- Lerner, J. S., Li, Y., Valdesolo, P., & Kassam, K. S. (2015). Emotion and decision making. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 66(1), 799–823. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010213-115043>
- Lin, C. H., Shih, H. Y., & Sher, P. J. (2007). Integrating technology readiness into technology acceptance: The TRAM model. *Psychology and Marketing*, 24(7).
- Lo, C. K. (2023). What is the impact of ChatGPT on education? A rapid review of the literature. *Educational Sciences*, 13, 410.
- Lu, Y. (2019). Artificial intelligence: A survey on evolution, models, applications, and future trends. *Journal of Management Analytics*.
- Lune, H., & Berg, B. L. (2017). *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences* (9th ed.). Pearson.
- Lune, H., & Berg, B. (2017). Pearson Education Limited.
- Mao, Y., & Lu, Z. (2017). MeSH Now: Automatic MeSH indexing at PubMed scale via learning to rank. *J Biomed Semantics*, 8, 15.
- McCombes, S. (2023). How to use ChatGPT effectively for academic writing. *Scribbr*. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com>
- Marangunić, N., & Granić, A. (2015). Technology acceptance model: A literature review from 1986 to 2013. *Univ. Access Inf. Soc.*, 14(1), 81–95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-014-0348-1>
- Min, S., So, K.K.F., & Jeong, M. (2021). Consumer adoption of the Uber mobile application: Insights from diffusion of innovation theory and technology acceptance model. In *Future of Tourism Marketing* (pp. 2-15). Routledge.
- Mondal, H., & Mondal, S. (2023). ChatGPT in academic writing: Maximizing its benefits and minimizing the risks. *Indian J Ophthalmol.*, 71(12), 3600-3606. doi:10.4103/IJO.IJO_718_23
- Nagaty, K. (2022). The impact of ChatGPT on student learning and performance: Educational opportunities and challenges. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Technology in Education (ICTE 2022)*. SSRN.
- Nair, G. (2023). Contemporary educational technology for strategies tailored to educational applications. *ChatGPT: Applications, Opportunities, and Threats*. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v18i17.39019>
- Nicholas, D. (2019). How to choose a journal and write a cover letter. *Saudi J Anaesth.*, 13(Suppl 1), S35–41.
- Ngo, T.T.A. (2023). The perception by university students of the use of ChatGPT in education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 18(17), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v18i17.39019>
- Nguyen, A., Ngo, H.N., Hong, Y., Dang, B., & Nguyen, B.P.T. (2023). Ethical principles for artificial intelligence in education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(4), 4221-4241.

- Oudeyer, J., Stiglic, G., & Verbert, K. (2016). Explaining artificial intelligence with visual analytics in healthcare. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 12(1), e1427.
- Oravec, J.A. (2019). Artificial intelligence, automation, and social welfare: Some ethical and historical perspectives on technological overstatement and hyperbole. *Ethics and Social Welfare*, 13(1), 18-32.
- Ouyang, L., Wu, J., Jiang, X., Almeida, D., Wainwright, C.L., Mishkin, P., et al. (2022). Training language models to follow instructions with human feedback. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2203.02155>
- Pappas, M., & Drigas, A. (2016). Incorporation of artificial intelligence tutoring techniques in mathematics. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP)*, 6(4), 12–16.
- Partel, V., Kakarla, S.C., & Ampatzidis, Y. (2019). Development and evaluation of a low-cost and smart technology for precision weed management utilizing artificial intelligence. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 157, 339-350.
- Pavlik, J.V. (2023). Collaborating with ChatGPT: Considering the implications of generative artificial intelligence for journalism and media education. *J. Mass Commun. Educ.*, 78(1), 84–93. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10776958221149577>
- Perkins, M. (2023). Academic integrity considerations of AI large language models in the post-pandemic era: ChatGPT and beyond. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 20(2).
- Pillai, R., Sivathanu, B., Metri, B., & Kaushik, N. (2023). Students' adoption of AI-based teacher-bots (T-bots) for learning in higher education. *Information Technology and People*.
- Punar Özçelik, N., & Yangın Ekşi, G. (2024). Cultivating writing skills: The role of ChatGPT as a learning assistant—a case study. *Smart Learning Environments*, 11(1), 10.
- Liebreuz, M., Schleifer, R., Buadze, A., Bhugra, D., & Smith, A. (2023). Generating scholarly content with ChatGPT: Ethical challenges for medical publishing. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 5(3), e105–e106.
- Razdi, P. (2020). Formulation of research question-Stepwise approach. *J Indian Assoc Pediatr Surg.*, 24, 15–20.
- Rodriguez, et al. (2023). What is the impact of ChatGPT on education? A rapid review of the literature. *Education Sciences*, 13(4), 410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13040410>
- Rogers, E.M. (2010). *Diffusion of innovations* (4th ed.). Free Press.
- Rudolph, J., Tan, S., & Tan, S. (2023). ChatGPT: Bullshit spewer or the end of traditional assessments in higher education? *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching*, 6(1), 342-363.
- Sallam, M. (2022). The utility of ChatGPT as an example of large language models in healthcare education, research and practice: Systematic review on the future perspectives and potential limitations. *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.19.23286155>
- Salvagno, M., Taccone, F.S., & Gerli, A.G. (2023). Can artificial intelligence help for scientific writing? *Critical Care*, 27, 75.
- Scherer, R., Siddiq, F., & Tondeur, J. (2019). The technology acceptance model (TAM): A meta-analytic structural equation modeling approach to explaining teachers' adoption of digital technology in education. *Computers & Education*, 128, 13–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.09.009>
- Seoud, W. (2022). The impact of ChatGPT on student learning: A review of benefits and challenges. *SSRN*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4305694>
- Siegle, D. (2023). A role for ChatGPT and AI in gifted education. *Gifted Child Today*, 46(3), 211-219. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10762175231158329>
- Singh, H., & Singh, A. (2023). ChatGPT: Systematic review, applications, and agenda for multidisciplinary research. *Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies*, 11(4), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iotcps.2023.05.004>
- Shah, J., Shah, A., & Pietrobon, R. (2009). Scientific writing of novice researchers: What difficulties and encouragements do they encounter? *Academic Medicine*, 84, 511–516.
- Sharafi, M. (2023). Determinants of intention to use ChatGPT for educational purposes: A case study of Iranian EFL learners. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00478-6>
- Shoufan, A. (2023). Exploring students' perceptions of ChatGPT: Thematic analysis and follow-up survey. *IEEE Access*, 11, 38805–38818. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3268224>
- Shroff, R.H., Deneen, C.C., & Ng, E.M. (2011). Analysis of the technology acceptance model in examining students' behavioral intention to use an e-portfolio system.

- Slyke, R.V., et al. (2023). ChatGPT in teaching and learning: A systematic review. *Education Sciences*, 14(6), 643. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060643>
- Sok, S., & Heng, K. (2023). ChatGPT for education and research: A review of benefits and risks. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4378735>
- Strzelecki, A. (2023). Students' acceptance of ChatGPT in higher education: An extended UTAUT2 model. *Interactive Learning Environments*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2209881>
- Tam, S., Chen, L., & Leung, K. (2023). Students' acceptance of ChatGPT in higher education: An extended UTAUT2 model. *Innovative Higher Education*, 49(1), 223-245. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10755-023-09686-1>
- Tate, T.P., Doroudi, S., Ritchie, D., Xu, Y., & Warschauer, M. (2023). Educational research and AI-generated writing: Confronting the coming tsunami. *EdArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.35542/osf.io/4mec3>
- Thorp, H.H. (2023). ChatGPT is fun, but not an author. *Science*, 379, 313.
- Thuy, H. (2022). Exploring EFL students' attitudes and perceptions on plagiarism when using ChatGPT in Vietnamese universities. In *Global Issues in Language Education (Vol. 2, pp. 123-145)*. Asia TEFL.
- Tlili, A., Shehata, B., Adarkwah, M.A., Bozkurt, A., Hickey, D.T., & Huang, R., et al. (2023). What if the devil is my guardian angel: ChatGPT as a case study of using chatbots in education. *Smart Learning Environments*, 10, 1–24.
- Trust, T., Whalen, J., & Mouza, C. (2023). Editorial: ChatGPT: Challenges, opportunities, and implications for teacher education. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 23(1), 1–13.
- Valor, C., Antonetti, P., & Crisafulli, B. (2022). Emotions and consumers' adoption of innovations: An integrative review and research agenda. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 179, 121609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121609>
- Vanathi, M. (2023). Realms of publication ethics. *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology*, 71, 2929.
- Veletsianos, G., Kimmons, R., & Bondah, F. (2023). ChatGPT and higher education: Initial prevalence and areas of interest. *EDUCAUSE Review*. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2023/3/chatgpt-and-higher-education-initial-prevalence-and-areas-of-interest>
- Wang, T., et al. (2023). The influence of dialogic engagement and prominence on visual product placement in virtual reality videos. *Journal of Business Research*, 100, 493-502
- Warsono, H., Yuwono, T., & Putranti, I. (2023). Analyzing technology acceptance model for collaborative governance in public administration: Empirical evidence of digital governance and perceived ease of use. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 7(1), 41-48.
- William. (2023). AI, ChatGPT, and language as technology: Q&A with William Marcellino. RAND Corporation.
- Wisniewski, B., Zierer, K., & Hattie, J. (2020). The power of feedback revisited: A meta-analysis of educational feedback research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 3087. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03087>
- Wong, M. (2018). Unleashing the potential of chatbots in education: A state-of-the-art analysis. In *Academy of Management Annual Meeting*.
- Woolf, B. (1988). Intelligent tutoring systems: A survey. In *Exploring Artificial Intelligence*, 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-934613-67-5.50005-8>
- Wojciechowski, R., & Cellary, W. (2013). Evaluation of learners' attitude toward learning in ARIES augmented reality environments. *Computers & Education*, 68, 570-585.
- Xia, Y., et al. (2023). Is ChatGPT a good sentiment analyzer? A preliminary study. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.04339*.
- Xu, L., Sanders, L., Li, K., & Chow, J.C.L. (2023). Chatbot for health care and oncology applications using artificial intelligence.
- Yan, W., et al. (2023). The impact of ChatGPT on education: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 26(2), 20-37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060643>
- Yip, C., Han, N.R., & Sng, B.L. (2016). Legal and ethical issues in research. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*, 60, 684–688.
- Zach, H. (2020). Zach on leadership. <https://zachonleadership.com/introducing-zachgpt-your-ai-leadership-chatbot/>
- Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V.I., & Bond, M., et al. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – Where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 39.
- Zhai, X. (2022). ChatGPT for next generation science learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4331313>

Zhavoronkov, A. (2022). Rapamycin in the context of Pascal's Wager: Generative pretrained transformer perspective. *Oncoscience*, 9, 82-84.

Zheng, Y., et al. (2019). Preparing educators and students for ChatGPT and AI technology in higher education: Benefits, limitations, strategies, and implications. ResearchGate.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Cristyl Angle L. Sombrio

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Agriculture – Philippines

Linagyn G. Cubio, LPT

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Agriculture – Philippines